

Spatial Data Infrastructure Management Plan for NIGERIA

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Introduction

The Energy Commission of Nigeria is an agency responsible for the overall planning and coordination of government policies in the energy sector in all its ramifications. The functions of the Commission include national energy planning and analysis, energy information gathering and dissemination among others. The Spatial Data Infrastructure Project for the Nigeria will facilitate the availability of and access to spatial data to enable the use of geospatial analysis techniques to support the planning and development of energy infrastructure, energy demand and supply and consumption patterns in the country. The project aims to enhance the efficiency, effectiveness, and sustainability of energy planning in Nigeria by providing a spatial perspective that incorporates various factors, enabling informed decision-making and promoting a more balanced and integrated approach to energy development.

The key capabilities for the project include;

- Enable online access to a wide range of spatial information and services
- Enable integration of geographically distributed spatial information
- Enable collaboration by multilateral information exchange and synchronization
- Allow autonomous organizations to develop interdependent relationships in a distributed environment
- Facilitate the definition and sharing of spatial semantics

The project could provide policy recommendations and guidelines to support energy infrastructure planning in other states of Nigeria, in line with the current constitutional amendment which allows states to generate, transmit and distribute electricity in regions covered by the National grid within their borders. These recommendations may include strategies for data capture and harmonization optimizing resource utilization, improving energy access, promoting renewable energy deployment, and minimizing environmental impacts.

Stakeholders

1. Federal Ministry of Power
2. National Bureau of Statistics
3. Academia
4. Rural Electrification Agency
5. Nigeria National Petroleum Corporation
6. Central Bank of Nigeria
7. Energy Commission of Nigeria
8. Ministry of Petroleum Resources
10. National Agency for Science Engineering and Infrastructure
11. Federal Ministry of Environment
12. Nigeria Geological Survey Agency

- 13 National Space Research and Development Agency
- 14 NigCommSat
- 15 Federal Ministry of water Resources
- 16 Federal Ministry of Lands and Housing
17. Federal Ministry of Transportation
18. Nigeria Meteorological Agency
19. Federal Ministry of Defense
20. Nigeria Electricity Regulatory Commission
21. Federal Ministry of Health
22. Federal Ministry of Information

Hosting Institution

Energy Commission of Nigeria

Actors

- System Administrator
- Database Administrators
- Editors
- Cartographers
- Registered users
- Public

Data Policy/Governance

The section provides information on members of the committee who will ensure that the all data policy regulations and requirements of government are adhered to in the data lifecycle. (Creation, collection, storage, use, protection, access, sharing and deletion). Most data will be from government and private sector organizations that are either primary producers, users or consumers. Other of data otherwise not available will be acquired through direct survey by the ECN and National Bureau of Statistics.

Project steering committee

1. DG/CEO Energy Commission of Nigeria
2. Director Energy Information System Department ECN
3. Director Digitalization and Communications Technology Department ECN
4. Director Energy Planning ECN
5. Director Planning and statistics, Federal Ministry of Power
5. Director Energy and Environment Department National Bureau of Statistics

Working group for Data content

S/N	Official	Designation	Organization
1	Mr.Segun O	Chairman	ECN
2	Ms Zahira Aminu	Member	ECN
3	Mr I. Chonoko	Member	ECN
4	Dr. Abdulkabir Aliyu	Member	ECN
5	Mr. Olagujnju A	Member	NBS
6	Ms Usman Fatima	Member	NITDA
7	Abbas Musa	Member	Federal Ministry of Comms
8	Mr. Emeka Eze	Member	Nigeria geological survey Agency
9	Mr Idris Mohammed	Member	NASRDA
10	Ms Saima Isa	Member	NBS

[Software Policy](#)

The Software policy should ensure compliance with the existing regulations as provided in the Nigeria Information Technology Development Agency standards and promote responsible usage. In the case of licensed software incorporation, all necessary licences should be purchased and used according to the licence agreement to avoid legal issues. The use of opensource software for the SDI project is recommended. There should be regular updates of the software to newer versions

[Standards policy](#)

This section provides an overview of the standards policy for the SDI for the management sharing and interoperability of spatial data. These standards aim to ensure data quality, consistency and compatibility across various systems and applications. This policy applies to all spatial data collected, stored, managed and shared within the SDI including data acquired from external sources or created internally.

[Functional requirements](#)

User Story reference	Expectation	Acceptance criteria
1	As an energy planner, I want to be able to visualize the overall energy resources in the country, Visualize demand and supply	Given that all the spatial data is available in the databse, I should should be able to visualize, make analysis and display

	<p>So that I can priotize allocation of resources for energy access.</p>	<p>output in charts, tables and maps</p>
2	<p>As a system Administrator</p> <p>I want to be able to install and configure software, hardware and networks. Provide upgrades and perform debugging when the system encounters problem</p> <p>Monitor system performance and troubleshooting issues.</p> <p>Ensure Security and efficiency of IT infrastructure.</p> <p>So that I can provide an efficient working system.</p>	<p>The system should notify me whenever there is an attempt to breach security'</p> <p>It should also alert me for any system performance and troubleshooting issues.</p>
3	<p>As a Database Administrator</p> <p>I want to be able to manage the database access and permissions.</p> <p>Ensure that databases meet users' requirements.</p> <p>Liaise with programmers, applications/operational staff, IT project managers and other technical staff.</p> <p>Review and manage database security, integrity and backup procedures</p> <p>So that I can control access to the database, review user requirements and provide solutions.</p>	<p>The system should alert me whenever a new user is registered</p> <p>The system should count the number of users and display. It should allow me grant permissions to users.</p>
4	<p>As an Editor</p> <p>I want to be able to define the database schema which includes creating tables, specifying columns, data types, constraints, relationships</p>	<p>The system should allow users to query the data and automatically generate results</p>

	<p>and indexes to allow the user design the structure of the database.</p> <p>So that I can ensure that data is accurate, up-to-date, and accessible to users.</p>	
5. Registered Users	<p>As a registered user,</p> <p>I should have full access to the data and be able to view it or download.</p>	<p>I should be able to access data and download or use on the system</p>
6 Public	<p>As a member of the public,</p> <p>I want to see a user friendly interface that will enable me access data in simple steps. I should be able to create an account using my email.</p>	<p>I expect the system to be reliable and have available data for me to access.</p>
7. Cartographers	<p>As a Cartographer,</p> <p>I should be able to create informative and visually appealing maps</p> <p>I should be able to integrate data from different sources</p> <p>So that I can ensure quality and compatibility within the database.</p>	<p>The system should display maps with the correct scales, projections and symbology.</p>

Business rules/ non-functional requirements

- The system must be deployed on Galaxy backbone server
- The system must adhere to the guidelines for the management of personal data by public institutions in Nigeria
- The system must follow the Nigerian content development in Information and Communication Technology ICT
- A map must complete drawing within 2ms of opening

Data requirements

Dataset	Source	Link	Coverage	Format	Year	Resolution	Category / Theme	Do we have already?	Units
Population density	NPC	www.nationalpopulation.gov.ng	National	xml				Yes	
Administration boundarys	NGSA		National	shapefile				Yes	
Electricity Supply	ECN		National	csv				Yes	kW
Household Electricity Demand	ECN		National	xml				Yes	kWh
Captive Power	ECN		National	xls					kWh
Electricity grid network	TCN	www.tcn.gov.ng	National	shapefile				Yes	
Power Plants		https://energydata.info/dataset/nigeria-		GeoJason				Yes	

		power-plants-2015-							
River Network	NIHSA	https://energydata.info/dataset/303a502d-ab18-42ee-a795-f50934c8887c/resource/b7dfd123-e167-4afb-a062-1f64111fd626/download/river-network-hydro-power-study-co-was.gpkg		geopkg					Yes
Solar Potential	ECN			csv					Yes
Wind Potential	NIMET			GeoJson					Yes
Minigrid	REA			Shape files					Yes

Database design

System architecture

UI/UX

The user should find it easy to register, navigate, search and access data. See example below;

Fig 1: User registration

Fig 2: registration details

Fig 3: Data input form

Fig 3: Data review page

Roles, personnel and qualifications

S.No	Role	Name	Qualifications
1	System Administrator		
2	Database Administrator		
3	Editors		
4	Cartographers		

Working Groups

S.No	Name of Working Group	Chairman
1	Network and Access Control	Mr. Olu Felix
2	Metadata Standards	MA Mundu
3	Interoperability and data Exchange	Dr. Mustapha Ahmed
4	Data Content Standards	Segun Ogunfowora
5	Outreach and Communication	
6	Policy, Legal and Security	Ms Mariya Yaro
7	Data delivery and Capacity building	

Capacity Building

Capacity building is an important element of the SDI implementation strategy. Systems developers need to know how to interface with the infrastructure, and spatial data users need to understand and be comfortable with data discovery, visualization and access processes and any other spatial tools and applications that are provided by the SDI.

Taking advantage of the potential of a fully operational SDI requires a paradigm shift from a closed GIS environment to an open Web services environment.

Moreover, experienced spatial data users need to develop the awareness of the advantages of making this shift as well as develop the capacity to effectively employ the SDI. Such capacity can be built with online learning tools, webinars, seminars, workshops and courses, either through their own efforts or in cooperation with educational institutions. Efforts to have SDI capacity-building elements included in spatial information programs at colleges and universities will pay dividends by helping to ensure that future graduates will be equipped to become strong SDI users

Documentation

Documentation is an effective mechanism in capturing processes and actions that take place within the SDI for reference purpose and continuity. Documentation on system design, installation process and data content is included. Changes that may occur in data and software upgrades as well as definitions are also included.

[Training](#)

Training on GIS software Packages

Database Management

GIS Web tools

Geospatial Data

[Dissemination and communication](#)

There will be programs to inform and educate the public about the abundance of information and resources that comprise the SDI. This will be done through the print media, digital media as well as awareness campaigns and public enlightenment programmes. This includes short videos that describes the makeup of the SDI and how the reader can use it to increase the accessibility and visibility of an organization's data and services, as well as how to build an application with standards and specifications.

[Code Management](#)

This section provides the effective code management practices to promote collaboration, code reusability, maintainability and improve the overall quality of the database codebase. Version control systems such as Github will be used to track changes made to the database schema, stored procedures, functions, triggers and other database objects.

[Budget](#)

Source of funding for the project

- Government
 - ECN Capital Projects
 - Central Bank of Nigeria
 - Federal Ministry of Finance
- Development partners
 - World Bank
 - UNDP
 - SE4All
 - GIZ
- Private sector
 - Sterling Bank Plc
 - Dangote Group
 - Access Bank Plc

Budget

S/N	Item	Quantity	Unit Cost	Total Cost
1				
2				
3				
4				
5				
6				

Monitoring and evaluation

The SDI will implement robust monitoring and and evaluating procedures to track performance, identify areas for enhancement and ensure the provision of high quality spatial data to meet user needs effectively, The steps to be implemented are as follows;

- Data quality assessment
- Performance metrics
- User feedback and surveys
- Usage analytics
- Security and privacy assessment
- Stakeholder engagement
- Continuous improvement

Maintenance

To ensure quality performance and usability of the system, the following should be conducted regularly;

- Performance optimization
- Service monitoring
- System software updates
- User support and Training

Project schedule

Category	Task ID	Task Name	March	Apr	May	June	July	August	Sept	Oct
Data Collection	1	Identify data sources								
	2	Collect Geospatial data (satellite imagery, aerial photography, etc.)								
Data Processing	3	Data cleaning and validation								
	4	Georeferencing and projection conversion								
	5	Data integration and harmonization								
Metadata Creation	6	Define metadata standards and requirements								
	7	Subtask: Create metadata records for each dataset								
System Development	8	Identify system requirements								
	9	Design and develop the SDI architecture								
	10	Implement data storage and retrieval mechanisms								
Testing	11	Conduct unit testing for individual components								
	12	Perform system integration testing								
	13	Validate data interoperability and functionality								
Deployment	14	Plan and execute system deployment								
	15	Train users and administrators								
	16	Subtask: Monitor and evaluate system performance								

Fig 4: Project Schedule

Project is to begin March 2024 and end October 2024.

References:

chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/http://www.info-rac.org/en/infomap-system/draft_sdi_architecture_wd-1.pdf

<https://databank.energy.gov.ng>

/efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://unstats.un.org/unsd/geoinfo/rcc/docs/rcca10/E_Conf_103_14_PCIDEA_SDI%20Manual_ING_Final.pdf

<https://energydata.info/dataset/72eab52a-da83-4b75-8993-bc9defcc5e4e/resource/78efd2c1-0155-4f39-87ca-70d7c4763f59/download/powerplants.geojson>

<https://energydata.info/dataset/1a812945-1130-4acc-910a-f36fac56b6af/resource/3b61d4b8-a5a9-4149-8958-a7d41304f9b1/download/nga-popngappv2c2015unadj>

<https://tcn.gov.ng/>